

Reference data generation for evaluating pairwise registration algorithms

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ABSTRACT

Registration algorithms are used in various domains related to mechanical engineering, particularly in applications requiring advanced analysis and processing of measurement data. The registration process estimates geometric transformation parameters between different datasets with numerous and different registration methods and algorithms which require evaluations. In metrology, most algorithms validations are carried out using software measurement standards (i.e., reference data or software). While reference data generators were developed for the validation of basic statistical operations or fitting algorithms, registration algorithms still lack robust reference data generators based on a well-defined problem formulation. Therefore, this paper proposes a robust generator of reference data to evaluate pairwise registration algorithms in accordance with the ISO 5436-2 standard. Four Iterative Closest Point (ICP) algorithm variants (point-to-point, point-to-plane, plane-to-plane and point-to-quadric) are evaluated on generated reference data pairs with known optimal transformation parameters. Uncertainty evaluation with Monte-Carlo simulation was also carried out and discussed. The practical application of the validated ICP variant is demonstrated through its implementation in a traceable stereovision system, underscoring the relevance of the methodology in real-world scenarios.

1. Introduction

Registration has widespread applications in all domains including aeronautic, automotive, shipbuilding, etc. related to complex or large surface measurements [1], while establishing conformity assessment of manufactured parts or surface reconstruction for reverse engineering. Registration aims to merge measurements recorded by sensors with various sensitivities, accuracies and poses (positions and orientations) into a common coordinate system [2–5]. This process can be broadly divided into two classes: pairwise and groupwise registration. Pairwise registration, focusing on feature-based methods, encompasses four main categories: Iterative Closest Point (ICP) variants [6,7], Graph Matchings (GM) [8,9], Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM) [9], and Machine Learning (ML) techniques [10]. Groupwise registration, on the other hand, includes sequential, one-to-many, simultaneous, information theoretic-based, probability-based, and ML techniques [8,11], often employing multiple pairwise registrations.

Since many registration algorithms are available, validation becomes critical to guarantee their accuracy and reliability [12]. Validation

approaches [13] are generally categorized into white-box testing which involves an exhaustive code examination against its design which can be time-consuming and may require access to the source code, and black-box testing, which uses reference data or software for evaluation without accessing the internal structure of the software [13]. Black-box testing emphasizes the use of reference software capable of numerically stable operations and handling extreme cases [14,15], and a reference data generation approach that produces reference parameter values based on a well-defined problem formulation [12,14,16,17].

Reference data defined in ISO 5436-2 (2012) [18] for validating registration algorithms are lacking. Therefore, a generic framework for registration covering complex surfaces is developed, including the mathematical formulation. Based on the proposed framework, a reference data generator is implemented for a large variety of registration categories. The verification of registration algorithms using the generated reference data is investigated for one selected scenario. The validated ICP registration algorithm is tested on several measurement datasets recorded by a machine vision system for real-time applications with dense point cloud acquisition.

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Fig. 1. ICP processing on two point clouds.

This paper, organized into seven sections, presents the developed research on reference data generation for validating registration algorithms, in particular, variants of ICP. Section 2 reviews the current state of the art of ICP variants and existing evaluation approaches based on reference data for evaluating form assessment and statistical software. Section 3 introduces our proposed reference data generation method based on the null-space approach. Section 4 and Section 5 apply the generated reference datasets to ICP variants, including the comparison of biases using unconstrained and reference datasets, and performing uncertainty evaluations. In Section 6, the validated ICP variant is applied to experimental datasets obtained from an accurate fringe projection system on prismatic material standards dedicated to aeronautics applications. The paper concludes in Section 7 with a summary of our findings and their implications.

2. Variants of ICP registration method and evaluation approaches

2.1. General formulation of ICP variants and limitations

The common principle of numerous feature-based registration algorithms is the minimisation of distances between the point clouds and the underlying surface, which can be approximated by a set of points or

local surfaces as in ICP [6,7], or probability density functions as in GMM [9]. Other techniques such as ML [10], GM [8,9], sequential, one-to-many, and simultaneous [8,11] are efficient for coarse registration, but they do not rely on explicit noise modelling, so they are not covered by the proposed framework. With GMM, the underlying model is represented by a collection of distributions (i.e., kernel centres and variances) instead of a continuous surface. Likewise, DL techniques may employ intermediary geometric features or deep features, but the underlying model is not represented by a continuous surface. On the contrary, ICP registration may incorporate surface estimation to find accurate point correspondences. Thus, the most commonly used feature-based method for fine pairwise registration is the ICP algorithm [19,20], and is still widely used nowadays. The core principle of ICP algorithms is based on iterative detection of matches and estimation of the relative transformation between two point clouds. Usually, ICP follows the process illustrated in Fig. 1: (a) initial pose of two point clouds, (b) subsampling of points, (c) matching of points, (d) weighting and rejection of matches, and (e) estimation of the relative transformation from the minimization of an objective function [6,7,21]. The registration process is executed iteratively until a threshold criterion is reached.

The ICP objective function ϕ_{ICP} is expressed in Eq. (1) and detailed in Eq. (2) for point-to-point ICP distance, which depend on the matching

Fig. 2. Black-box testing procedures according to [18].

point $\hat{q}_i = \operatorname{argmin}_{p_j} \|\mathbf{T}(\boldsymbol{\tau})\mathbf{p}_i - \mathbf{p}_j\|_2$ with \mathbf{p}_j in the target point cloud.

$$\phi_{\text{ICP}}(\boldsymbol{\tau}) = \sum_{i=1}^m \hat{d}_i(\boldsymbol{\tau})^2 \quad (1)$$

$$\hat{d}_i(\boldsymbol{\tau}) = \|\mathbf{T}(\boldsymbol{\tau})\mathbf{p}_i - \hat{q}_i\|_2 \quad (2)$$

Other distances are investigated in the literature such as the point-to-plane [20], plane-to-plane [22] and point-to-quadric [23] distances formulated in Eqs. (3), (4) and (5), respectively (“ \top ” is the transpose operation and \mathbf{A} is the matrix form of the quadric).

$$\hat{d}_i = (\mathbf{T}(\boldsymbol{\tau})\mathbf{p}_i - \hat{q}_i)^\top \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i \quad (3)$$

$$\hat{d}_i = (\mathbf{T}(\boldsymbol{\tau})\mathbf{p}_i - \hat{q}_i)^\top (\mathbf{T}(\boldsymbol{\tau})\mathbf{n}_i + \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i) \quad (4)$$

$$\hat{d}_i^2 = (\mathbf{T}(\boldsymbol{\tau})\mathbf{p}_i)^\top \mathbf{A}(\hat{q}_i) (\mathbf{T}(\boldsymbol{\tau})\mathbf{p}_i) \quad (5)$$

The relative transformation $\mathbf{T}(\boldsymbol{\tau})$ can be classified as either rigid or non-rigid [24]. For transformation parameters $\boldsymbol{\tau} = [\mathbf{t}, \boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{s}] = [t_1, t_2, t_3, \theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3, s_1, s_2, s_3]$ the transformation matrix is expressed in Eq. (6) with s_j the scaling factors, t_j the translations, and \mathbf{R}_j the 3D rotation matrices with θ_j angles. Each parameter is decomposed into its x , y and z components.

$$\mathbf{T}(\boldsymbol{\tau}) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{s}) & \mathbf{t} \\ \mathbf{0} & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_1(\theta_1)\mathbf{R}_2(\theta_2)\mathbf{R}_3(\theta_3) & \begin{bmatrix} s_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & s_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & s_3 \end{bmatrix} & \begin{bmatrix} t_1 \\ t_2 \\ t_3 \end{bmatrix} \\ \mathbf{0} & & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The accuracy of the estimated transformation is calculated with a performance measure: the difference between the ideal transformation \mathbf{T}^* and estimated transformation $\hat{\mathbf{T}}$. Commonly used metrics are defined as the difference in translation (7), or rotation (8) [11].

$$\Delta t = \|\hat{\mathbf{t}} - \mathbf{t}^*\|_2 \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta \theta = \arccos((\operatorname{trace}(\hat{\mathbf{R}}^\top \mathbf{R}^*) - 1)/2) \quad (8)$$

The accuracy of the transformation parameters \mathbf{t} , $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ and \mathbf{s} can be affected by numerous influence factors: point density, overlaps, measurement noise, outliers, etc. Moreover, point cloud symmetries or large

initial relative transformations can lead to local optimum solutions [9,21]. Since registration algorithms are sensitive to many influence factors, an evaluation on datasets obtained from real measurements or simulations becomes essential. Here, simulations are more appropriate to obtain datasets associated to predefined influence factors. Datasets could be generated through the sampling of a surface model combined with simulated Gaussian noise and relative transformations.

2.2. Reference data generator for evaluating form assessment and statistical software

The evaluation of metrological software is discussed in ISO standard documents. In the field of surface texture measurement, ISO 5436-2 (2012) [18] introduces the concept of software measurement standards (Fig. 2). These standards are defined as “reference data or reference software intended to reproduce the value of a measurand with known uncertainty in order to verify the software (i.e., filter algorithms, parameter calculations, etc.) used to calculate the measurand in a measuring instrument”.

A strategy to generate reference datasets for evaluating software was developed for basic statistical operations [12,16,17,25] including average calculation, standard deviation, Principal Component Analysis (PCA), linear Least-Square regression (LS), etc. For LS regression, the optimal solution can be expressed in closed-form by the Eq. (9).

$$\hat{\mathbf{a}} = \operatorname{argmin}_{\mathbf{a}} \phi_{\text{LS}}(\mathbf{a}) = \operatorname{argmin}_{\mathbf{a}} \sum_{i=1}^m d_i(\mathbf{a})^2 = (\mathbf{M}^\top \mathbf{M})^{-1} \mathbf{M}^\top \mathbf{y} \quad (9)$$

$\mathbf{M} \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times m}(\mathbb{R})$ is a design matrix, $\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{R}^k$ is a parameter vector, $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is a response vector, and $\mathbf{d} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is a deviation vector. A common approach to generate testing datasets for evaluating LS software is to combine random errors \mathbf{d}^* (e.g., Gaussian noise) and a linear model with predefined parameters \mathbf{a}^* to generate responses $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{M}\mathbf{a}^* + \mathbf{d}^*$. Nevertheless, the optimal solution of the objective function ϕ_{LS} (Eq. (9)), yields values of parameters $\hat{\mathbf{a}}$ that are usually different from the predefined parameters \mathbf{a}^* . Therefore, the evaluation of a software with this testing datasets could provide a biased performance measure.

To mitigate the bias, Cook et al. [25] generated testing datasets such that the best fit of the noisy data is reached at the predefined parameter values \mathbf{a}^* . In this case, $\mathbf{d}^* = \mathbf{Q}_2^* \boldsymbol{\nu}$ is a vector selected in the null-space of \mathbf{M}^\top . $\boldsymbol{\nu} \in \mathbb{R}^{m-k}$ is an arbitrary vector, and \mathbf{Q}_2^* is a null-space basis obtained from a decomposition of \mathbf{M}^\top . Consequently, the parameters minimizing ϕ_{LS} could be equal to the predefined parameters, as proven in Eq. (10).

$$\hat{\mathbf{a}} = (\mathbf{M}^\top \mathbf{M})^{-1} \mathbf{M}^\top \mathbf{y} = \underbrace{(\mathbf{M}^\top \mathbf{M})^{-1} \mathbf{M}^\top \mathbf{M}}_{\mathbf{I}} \mathbf{a}^* + \underbrace{(\mathbf{M}^\top \mathbf{M})^{-1} \mathbf{M}^\top \mathbf{Q}_2^* \boldsymbol{\nu}}_{\mathbf{0}} = \mathbf{a}^* \quad (10)$$

A similar strategy to generate reference datasets for evaluating software dedicated to form assessment (e.g., minimum zone fitting and Total Least-Square (TLS) regressions) was investigated in 1992 [14] by Forbes and Cox, and extended in [26,27]. For TLS regression [14], the problem is formulated mathematically with the objective function $\phi_{\text{TLS}}(\boldsymbol{\tau}, \mathbf{a})$ that could be minimized with respect to k transformation parameters $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ and shape parameters \mathbf{a} (11).

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}, \hat{\mathbf{a}} = \operatorname{argmin}_{\boldsymbol{\tau}, \mathbf{a}} \phi_{\text{TLS}}(\boldsymbol{\tau}, \mathbf{a}) = \operatorname{argmin}_{\boldsymbol{\tau}, \mathbf{a}} \sum_{i=1}^m d_i(\boldsymbol{\tau}, \mathbf{a})^2 \quad (11)$$

$d_i = \text{def} (\mathbf{q}_i - \mathbf{p}_i)^\top \mathbf{n}_i$ is the deviation, \mathbf{q}_i is the 3D footpoint closest to \mathbf{p}_i , and \mathbf{n}_i is the normal vector at \mathbf{q}_i .

The optimality conditions are stated in the following Eq. (12).

$$\begin{aligned} (\boldsymbol{\tau}^*, \mathbf{a}^*) \text{ is a strict local minimum of } \phi_{\text{TLS}} &\Leftrightarrow \nabla \phi_{\text{TLS}}(\boldsymbol{\tau}^*, \mathbf{a}^*) \\ &= \mathbf{0} \text{ and } \mathbf{H}_{\phi_{\text{TLS}}}(\boldsymbol{\tau}^*, \mathbf{a}^*) \text{ is strictly positive definite} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$\nabla \phi_{\text{TLS}} = 2\mathbf{J}_d^\top \mathbf{d}$ is the gradient vector and $\mathbf{H}_{\phi_{\text{TLS}}}$ is the Hessian matrix. Similarly to LS regression, testing datasets can be generated such as to

Fig. 3. Illustration of distances between the points and underlying surfaces (— source and — target) in the source and target datasets with $p_i = \tilde{q}_i + d_i \tilde{n}_i$

verify the condition on $\nabla \phi_{\text{TLS}}$ (Eq. (13)).

$$p_i^* = q_i^* + d_i^* n_i^* = q_i^* + (Q_2^* \nu)^* n_i^* \quad (13)$$

$\nu \in \mathbb{R}^{m-k}$ is an arbitrary vector, and Q_2^* is a null-space basis obtained from a decomposition of $J_d^T(\tau^*, a^*)$.

Overall, the method for generating testing datasets can be split in two steps: (1) defining the problem formulation, and (2) generating datasets satisfying the optimality conditions such that the predefined and optimal parameter values are equal. The second step can be achieved by applying the null-space data generation approach. At present, testing datasets were investigated for the previously mentioned statistical operations and form assessment software.

3. Reference datasets generation for registration

The implemented generator of reference datasets for evaluating registration algorithms is based on the two-step method published by Forbes *et al.* [14]. This method includes the problem formulation of pairwise registration based on several assumptions (Gaussian noise, rigid transformation, outlier bounds, etc., often used in ICP algorithms) and the optimality condition formulation. Therefore, the generated data can be applied to algorithms based on similar assumptions or approximating this mathematical formulation. The optimality condition formulations are modified for time and memory efficient calculations.

3.1. Problem formulation of ICP variants registration

The problems of point-to-point [19], point-to-plane [20], plane-to-plane [22], or point-to-quadric [23] ICP are formulated as the minimization of the distances between matched points p_i in the source point cloud $\mathcal{P}^{(1)}$ and p_j in the target point cloud $\mathcal{P}^{(2)}$ (Eq. (1)). The common principle lies in the projection of each point p_i in the source point cloud to a point on a local approximated surface in the target point cloud, which is a plane or a quadric in the case of point-to-plane or point-to-quadric ICP. The local approximated surface allows to estimate the underlying surface $\mathcal{S}^{(2)}$, as claimed by Mitra *et al.* in [23]. Hence, the problem formulation becomes the minimization of distances between each p_i and their projection \tilde{q}_i on the underlying surface $\mathcal{S}^{(2)}$. In addition, a symmetric objective function leads to obtain unique registration results, by considering an additional term depending on the inverse relative transformation of $\mathcal{P}^{(2)}$ [28].

The proposed registration is formulated as a non-linear regression problem. The objective function to minimize is expressed in Eq. (14), which depend on the deviations $d_i(\tau)$ between the source and target point clouds (Fig. 3).

$$\phi(\tau) = \sum_{i=1}^{m_1+m_2} d_i(\tau)^2 = \mathbf{d}(\tau)^T \mathbf{d}(\tau) \quad (14)$$

- $d_i(\tau) = (\tilde{q}_i(\tau) - p_i)^T \tilde{n}_i(\tau)$ is the signed distance between p_i and the underlying surface
- $\tilde{q}_i(\tau) = \begin{cases} T(\tau)q_i(\tau) & \text{for } i \leq m_1 \\ T^{-1}(\tau)q_i(\tau) & \text{for } i > m_1 \end{cases}$ is the 3D footpoint on the underlying surface closest to p_i
- $\tilde{n}_i(\tau) = \begin{cases} T(\tau)^{-T}n_i(\tau) & \text{for } i \leq m_1 \\ T(\tau)^T n_i(\tau) & \text{for } i > m_1 \end{cases}$ is the normal vector at $\tilde{q}_i(\tau)$ with “ $-T$ ” the inverse transpose
- $u_i(\tau) = \begin{cases} \operatorname{argmin}_u \|p_i - T(\tau)q(u)\|_2^2 & \text{for } i \leq m_1 \\ \operatorname{argmin}_u \|p_i - T^{-1}(\tau)q(u)\|_2^2 & \text{for } i > m_1 \end{cases}$ is the 2D footpoint to express the coordinates on the surface for $q_i(\tau) = q(u_i(\tau))$ and $n_i(\tau) = n(u_i(\tau))$
- $\tau = [t, \theta, s] = [t_1, t_2, t_3, \theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3, s_1, s_2, s_3]$ is the relative transformation parameter vector with the transformation matrix $T(\tau)$ expressed in Eq. (6).

Since measurement datasets usually include outliers related to either tactile or optical scanning systems, outliers definition is taken into account in the problem formulation using a truncated reformulation of Eq. (14). The reformulation in Eq. (15) introduces a bound $c\sigma$ for each defined outlier as the minimum orthogonal distance from the underlying surface. Considering d_i sampled from a Gaussian distribution with standard deviation σ , and $p = 0.05$ the probability that d_i is an outlier (i. e., $d_i^2 \geq c^2 \sigma^2$), then c should be approximately equal to 3.

$$\phi(\tau) = \sum_{i=1}^{m_1+m_2} \min(d_i(\tau)^2, c^2 \sigma^2) \quad (15)$$

3.2. Null-space determination for reference data generation

The proposed approach for generating reference data addresses the dual problem of registration: for given transformation parameters τ^* , footpoints q_i^* and normal n_i^* , how to generate point deviations d_i^* and points p_i^* , for which the objective function $\phi(\tau^*)$ is minimum? Two sufficient conditions are required to obtain a strict local minimum of $\phi(\tau^*)$: (1) the gradient $\nabla \phi$ applied in τ^* should be equal to the null vector (Eq. (16)), and (2) the Hessian matrix H_ϕ applied in τ^* should be strictly positive definite (Eq. (17)).

$$\nabla \phi^* = 2J_d^{*T} \mathbf{d}^* = \mathbf{0} \quad (16)$$

$$H_\phi^* = 2J_d^{*T} J_d^* + 2 \sum_{i=1}^m d_i^* H_{d_i}^* \succ \mathbf{0} \quad (17)$$

Fig. 4. Illustration of reference data generation for the source point cloud (— underlying surface, × predefined source points $\check{p}_i = q_i^* + \check{d}_i n_i^*$, and • reference source points $p_i = q_i^* + d_i^* n_i^*$).

Fig. 5. Illustration of ill-defined deviations d_i^* due to: (a) $d_i^* > r_i$, (b) d_i^* generated by Eq. (21), (c) complex shape, (d) mesh representation of surfaces.

$\nabla\phi^*$, J_d^* , H_ϕ^* and $H_{d_i}^*$ are the gradient, Jacobian and Hessians applied in τ^* , $m = m_1 + m_2$ is the number of points in both points clouds, and \succ is the symbol for a strictly positive definite matrix, meaning that all the eigenvalues of H_ϕ^* are strictly positive. The Jacobian J_d^* should be full-rank with $\text{rank}(J_d^*) = \text{length}(\tau) = k$. The full-rank is a necessary condition that should be verified to solve Eqs. (16) and (17). For shapes invariant by translations or rotations, the Jacobian becomes rank-deficient, then the condition is not satisfied. Geometrical characteristics due to manufacturing process could be considered to eliminate invariances.

The Eq. (16) can be solved by computing the null-space basis of $J_d^{*\top}$ using the formulation in Eq. (18). This formulation is based on a QR decomposition with $R_1^* \in \mathcal{R}_k(\mathbb{R})$ upper triangular and $Q_d^* \in \mathcal{O}_m(\mathbb{R})$ such that $Q_1^{*\top} Q_2^* = 0$. Then, deviations satisfying (18) can be generated using Eq. (19) with an arbitrary vector $\nu \in \mathbb{R}^{m-k}$.

$$J_d^{*\top} d^* = (Q_d^* R_d^*)^\top d^* = [R_1^{*\top} \quad 0] [Q_1^* \quad Q_2^*]^\top d^* = R_1^{*\top} Q_1^{*\top} d^* = 0 \quad (18)$$

$$d^* = Q_2^* \nu \quad (19)$$

The Hessian H_ϕ^* in Eq. (17) is strictly definite positive if J_d^* is full rank and $\|\sum_{i=1}^m d_i^* H_{d_i}^*\|$ is sufficiently small compared to the smallest eigenvalue λ_{\min} of $J_d^{*\top} J_d^*$ [29]. Here, it is assumed that all $\|H_{d_i}^*\|$ are close to 1, and $\|d^*\|$ is compared to λ_{\min} .

Since an arbitrary vector ν cannot be used to mimic a specific distribution of deviations (e.g., Gaussian noise), predefined deviations $\check{d} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ are considered in the Eq. (20). The resolution of the LS problem expressed in Eq. (20) gives the appropriate deviations d^* . The generated deviations d^* are illustrated, only in the source point cloud, in Fig. 4 for predefined deviations \check{d} . Similarly, reference data is generated for the target point cloud.

$$d^* = Q_2^* \underset{\nu}{\text{argmin}} \left\| Q_2^* \nu - \check{d} \right\|_2 = Q_2^* Q_2^{*\top} \check{d} \quad (20)$$

The computation of the null-space basis Q_2^* is time and memory

Fig. 6. Flowchart for the generation of reference and unconstrained deviations.

consuming. The number of iterations can be reduced by computing the range-space basis \mathbf{Q}_1^* instead of the null-space, and reformulating the Eq. (20) as in (21). The proposed novel Eq. (21) considers the properties of the matrix \mathbf{Q}_d^* , i.e. $\mathbf{Q}_d^* \mathbf{Q}_d^{*\top} = \mathbf{Q}_1^* \mathbf{Q}_1^{*\top} + \mathbf{Q}_2^* \mathbf{Q}_2^{*\top} = \mathbf{I}$.

$$\mathbf{d}^* = \tilde{\mathbf{d}} - \mathbf{Q}_1^* (\mathbf{Q}_1^{*\top} \tilde{\mathbf{d}}) \quad (21)$$

The computation of the range-space basis \mathbf{Q}_1^* depends on the given components of the Jacobian \mathbf{J}_d^* . This formulation is different from the TLS regressions used in [14] by considering the inverse transformation for the target point cloud in Eq. (14). The Jacobian \mathbf{J}_d could be obtained by calculating the partial derivatives of the deviations d_i as in Eq. (22).

$$(\mathbf{J}_d)_{ij} = \frac{\partial d_i}{\partial \tau_j} = \begin{cases} -\mathbf{q}_i^{*\top} \frac{\partial \mathbf{T}}{\partial \tau_j} \mathbf{T}^{-\top} \mathbf{n}_i & \text{for } i \leq m_1 \\ -\mathbf{q}_i^{*\top} \frac{\partial \mathbf{T}}{\partial \tau_j} \mathbf{T}^{-\top} \mathbf{n}_i & \text{for } i > m_1 \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

Fig. 7. Surface models of selected parts from the aeronautic.

The application of \mathbf{J}_d at $\tau^* = [0, 0, 1]$ allows to obtain \mathbf{J}_d^* . The partial derivative of deviations d_i at τ^* with respect to translation, rotation and scaling parameters are expressed in Eqs. (23), (24) and (25). The derivative of the transformation matrix \mathbf{T} (Eq. (6)) depends on the vector product “ \times ” and the skew symmetric matrix $[\mathbf{e}_j]_{\times}$ with axis \mathbf{e}_j .

$$\frac{\partial d_i^*}{\partial \tau_j} = \begin{cases} -\mathbf{q}_i^{*\top} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & -\mathbf{e}_j \\ \mathbf{0} & 1 \end{bmatrix}^{\top} \mathbf{n}_i^* = n_{ij}^* & \text{for } i \leq m_1 \\ -\mathbf{q}_i^{*\top} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{e}_j \\ \mathbf{0} & 1 \end{bmatrix}^{\top} \mathbf{n}_i^* = -n_{ij}^* & \text{for } i > m_1 \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{\partial d_i^*}{\partial \theta_j} = \begin{cases} -\mathbf{q}_i^{*\top} \begin{bmatrix} [\mathbf{e}_j]_{\times} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & 1 \end{bmatrix}^{\top} \mathbf{n}_i^* = (\mathbf{q}_i^* \times \mathbf{n}_i^*)_j & \text{for } i \leq m_1 \\ -\mathbf{q}_i^{*\top} \begin{bmatrix} [\mathbf{e}_j]_{\times} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & 1 \end{bmatrix}^{\top} \mathbf{n}_i^* = -(\mathbf{q}_i^* \times \mathbf{n}_i^*)_j & \text{for } i > m_1 \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{\partial d_i^*}{\partial s_j} = \begin{cases} -\mathbf{q}_i^{*\top} \begin{bmatrix} -\mathbf{e}_j \mathbf{e}_j^{\top} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & 1 \end{bmatrix}^{\top} \mathbf{n}_i^* = q_{ij}^* n_{ij}^* & \text{for } i \leq m_1 \\ -\mathbf{q}_i^{*\top} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{e}_j \mathbf{e}_j^{\top} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & 1 \end{bmatrix}^{\top} \mathbf{n}_i^* = -q_{ij}^* n_{ij}^* & \text{for } i > m_1 \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

The Jacobian matrix can be constructed as shown in Eq. (26), where “ \odot ” is the elementwise multiplication.

$$\mathbf{J}_d^{*\top} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{n}_1^* & \dots & \mathbf{n}_{m_1}^* & -\mathbf{n}_{m_1+1}^* & \dots & -\mathbf{n}_{m_1+m_2}^* \\ \mathbf{q}_1^* \times \mathbf{n}_1^* & \dots & \mathbf{q}_{m_1}^* \times \mathbf{n}_{m_1}^* & -\mathbf{q}_{m_1+1}^* \times \mathbf{n}_{m_1+1}^* & \dots & -\mathbf{q}_{m_1+m_2}^* \times \mathbf{n}_{m_1+m_2}^* \\ \mathbf{q}_1^* \odot \mathbf{n}_1^* & \dots & \mathbf{q}_{m_1}^* \odot \mathbf{n}_{m_1}^* & -\mathbf{q}_{m_1+1}^* \odot \mathbf{n}_{m_1+1}^* & \dots & -\mathbf{q}_{m_1+m_2}^* \odot \mathbf{n}_{m_1+m_2}^* \end{bmatrix} \quad (26)$$

The QR decomposition of $\mathbf{J}_d^{*\top}$ gives the range-space basis \mathbf{Q}_1^* used in Eq. (21) to construct reference data. The computation of the range-space has a time complexity in $\mathcal{O}(mk)$ instead of $\mathcal{O}(m^2k)$ for the null-space. Moreover, the execution order of terms of Eq. (21) under brackets guarantee low time and memory complexities in $\mathcal{O}(mk)$ for matrix multiplications.

Fig. 8. Uniformly sampled footpoints \mathbf{q}_i^* (10^5 points for each dataset pair).

3.3. Well-defined closest point bounds

The registration problem formulated in Eq. (14) is function of points \mathbf{p}_i , expressed as $\mathbf{q}_i^* + d_i^* \mathbf{n}_i^*$ with \mathbf{q}_i^* defined as the closest point to \mathbf{p}_i on the surface. Nonetheless, \mathbf{q}_i^* used for data generation might contradict the previous definition. This issue could arise when large deviations d_i^* are considered as shown in Fig. 5(a). Thus, Forbes *et al.* suggested the application of small deviations below the radius of curvature r_i at \mathbf{q}_i^* [14]. Even if this suggestion could solve the problem, it remains insufficient for three reasons:

1. Fig. 5(b): there is no guarantee that deviations \mathbf{d}^* generated by Eq. (21) are smaller than the radius of curvature even if small predefined deviations $\check{\mathbf{d}}$ are considered.
2. Fig. 5(c): for this specific complex shape, deviations \mathbf{d}^* might satisfy the condition related to the radius of curvature, but the actual closest-point $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_i$ to \mathbf{p}_i is different from \mathbf{q}_i^* .
3. Fig. 5(d): for points sampled on meshes, the radii of curvature are infinite, and the condition becomes insufficient.

An iterative process is implemented to solve the problems illustrated in Fig. 5(a, c and d) through empirical estimation of the minimum and maximum well-defined deviations. Initially, the maximum or minimum deviation $d_i^{(0)}$ is set to be at least smaller than the outlier bound 3σ or radius of curvature. Then, at iteration t , $d_i^{(t+1)}$ is calculated by the Eq. (27) until the estimated closest point $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_i^{(t)}$ to $\mathbf{q}_i^* + d_i^{(t)} \mathbf{n}_i^*$ is equal to \mathbf{q}_i^* .

$$d_i^{(t+1)} = \epsilon_d \frac{\hat{d}_i^{(t)} - d_i^{(t)} \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i^{(t)\top} \mathbf{n}_i^*}{\text{sign}(\hat{\mathbf{n}}_i^{(t)\top} (\mathbf{q}_i^* - \hat{\mathbf{q}}_i^{(t)})) \text{sign}(d_i^{(t)} - \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i^{(t)\top} \mathbf{n}_i^*)} \quad (27)$$

where $\hat{d}_i^{(t)}$ is the estimated distance, $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_i^{(t)}$ is the normal at $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_i^{(t)}$ and $0 < \epsilon_d < 1$.

Since the local surface at $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_i^{(t)}$ is assumed to be a plane, the execution of Eq. (27) will yield $\mathbf{q}_i^* + d_i^{(t+1)} \mathbf{n}_i^*$ closer to point \mathbf{q}_i^* instead of the local surface at $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_i^{(t)}$. The iterative process allows to identify a global envelop

defined with upper and lower boundaries \mathbf{d}_{\max} and \mathbf{d}_{\min} calculated at each footpoint \mathbf{q}_i^* . As the estimation of boundaries for each footpoint is independent, the footpoints can be processed in parallel for an efficient estimation of \mathbf{d}_{\min} and \mathbf{d}_{\max} . Then, the reference data could be generated such that deviations are ranged in $\mathbf{d}_{\min} \leq \mathbf{d}^* \leq \mathbf{d}_{\max}$.

Furthermore, to solve the problem illustrated in Fig. 5(b), a non-linear convex optimization is applied to update the predefined deviations $\check{\mathbf{d}}$ by minimizing the function $\|\check{\mathbf{d}} - \mathbf{d}\|_2$. Moreover, the minimization is bounded as formulated in Eq. (28) with intermediary variables \mathbf{c}_{\min} and \mathbf{c}_{\max} positive and $\nu \in \mathbb{R}^k$. A sparse matrix format is adopted for memory complexity reasons. Moreover, the solver is initialized beforehand with factorization caching for improving the computational efficiency of Monte-Carlo simulations. Only $\check{\mathbf{d}}$ has to be updated in the solver for each simulation, and the factorization caching can be achieved with the Operator Splitting Quadratic Program (OSQP) solver [30].

$$\begin{cases} \nu = \mathbf{Q}_1^{*\top} \mathbf{d} \\ \mathbf{d}_{\min} \leq \mathbf{d} - \mathbf{Q}_1^* \nu \leq \mathbf{d}_{\max} \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Q}_1^{*\top} & -\mathbf{I}_{k \times k} \\ -\mathbf{I}_{m \times m} & \mathbf{Q}_1^* \\ \mathbf{I}_{m \times m} & -\mathbf{Q}_1^* \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{d} \\ \nu \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{m+k} \\ \mathbf{c}_{\min} \\ \mathbf{c}_{\max} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{m+k} \\ -\mathbf{d}_{\min} \\ \mathbf{d}_{\max} \end{bmatrix} \quad (28)$$

Once the convex optimization convergence is reached, deviations \mathbf{d}^* are calculated with Eq. (21), and reference points $\mathbf{p}_i = \mathbf{q}_i^* + d_i^* \mathbf{n}_i^*$ are generated with the code detailed in Fig. 6.

4. Validation method for reference data generation

For users intending to verify their registration software, only the predefined footpoints sampling, noise amplitude, and transformation amplitude need to be provided for mimicking measurements representative of their specific systems and environments. Here, reference and unconstrained datasets are generated for 3 complex shapes (impeller, turbine blade and winglet) with medium-size commonly used in the aeronautic domain (Fig. 7). A uniform sampling of the surface model (Fig. 8) is combined with a predefined Gaussian noise $\check{\mathbf{d}}$ (standard

Fig. 9. Flowchart for the generation of a reference dataset pair.

Table 1

Medians of differences between optimal and predefined parameters (rotation $\tilde{\Delta}\theta$ or translation $\tilde{\Delta}t$) for unconstrained and reference datasets, calculated over 60 Monte-Carlo simulations.

Mechanical part	Median $\tilde{\Delta}\theta$ ($\times 10^{-3}$ deg)		Median $\tilde{\Delta}t$ (μm)	
	Unconstrained dataset pair	Reference dataset pair	Unconstrained dataset pair	Reference dataset pair
impeller	0.85	2.02×10^{-11}	0.35	5.24×10^{-12}
turbine blade	0.57	1.01×10^{-11}	0.49	2.55×10^{-11}
winglet	0.22	1.20×10^{-11}	0.21	8.99×10^{-12}

Fig. 10. Flowchart of the evaluation of a registration software with Monte-Carlo simulations.

deviation $\sigma = 0.1$ mm) and a predefined rigid relative transformation (a rotational angle in the range $0 < \theta < 5$ deg, and a translation norm in the range $0 < t < 5$ mm). Both standard deviation and relative transformation amplitudes are selected such as to be similar to experimental noise and transformation identified when using stereovision systems. For each selected mechanical part, a dataset pair is generated with respect to the flowchart presented in Fig. 9.

According to Cox and Harris [12], the accuracy of generated datasets could be evaluated by assessing the closeness of $\|J_d^{*T} d^* / \|J_d^{*T} \| \|d^*\|$ to zero. Even if this method allows to verify the accuracy of the generated dataset pairs, it does not provide the difference between predefined and optimal transformation parameters. To obtain the optimal transformation parameters, an iterative minimization of the objective function presented in Eq. (14) is implemented.

For validating the procedure of reference data generation, two metrics are defined to calculate the difference between optimal and predefined transformation parameters: $\Delta\theta$ for rotation and Δt for translation. The metrics are calculated and compared for both unconstrained and reference datasets. Monte-Carlo simulations are applied for propagating standard deviations in relation to the initial transformations and point deviations through the tested registration algorithms. The selected rotation range vary between 0 and 5 degrees, translations between 0 and 5 mm, and the Gaussian noise equals to $\sigma = 0.1$ mm. A regular sampling of the selected surface is considered. 60 Monte-Carlo simulations are carried out and the returned medians of rotation $\tilde{\Delta}\theta$ and translation $\tilde{\Delta}t$ are reported in Table 1. For reference dataset pairs, the medians $\tilde{\Delta}\theta$ and $\tilde{\Delta}t$ are close to zero ($\approx 10^{-14}$, which correspond to the limited accuracy of floating point representation). Those results validate the accuracy of the generated reference dataset pairs in comparison to unconstrained dataset pairs.

5. Evaluation of the selected ICP variant on generated reference datasets

The selected ICP variants are the point-to-point (OF₄) [19], point-to-

Fig. 11. Errors on rotation and translation parameters returned by the selected ICP variant.

plane (OF_3) [20], plane-to-plane (OF_2) [22] and point-to-quadric (OF_1) [23] distances. The rejection step is based on distance and normal orientation, and combined with decreasing thresholds. The stopping criteria rely on the convergence of the estimated transformation [31]. The generated dataset pairs and relative transformations for validation (reference and unconstrained datasets) are reused for testing the selected ICP variant with respect to the flowchart illustrated in Fig. 10.

The initial misaligned dataset pairs (either reference or unconstrained) are set to the ICP variant, and the metrics Δt and $\Delta\theta$ given in Eqs. (7) and (8) are calculated, while evaluating the accuracy of the

estimated transformation parameters $\hat{\tau}$ (Fig. 11). The medians $\tilde{\Delta t}$ and $\tilde{\Delta\theta}$ and confidence intervals calculated with Monte-Carlo simulations over 60 iterations are illustrated in Fig. 11. The main results of the ICP variant evaluation associated to the four objective functions on reference and unconstrained dataset pairs, including medians and relative variations, are reported and compared in Table 2.

The comparison of medians reported in both Table 1 ($\tilde{\Delta\theta} \approx 10^{-14}$ deg and $\tilde{\Delta t} \approx 10^{-11}$ μm) and Table 2 ($\tilde{\Delta\theta} \approx 10^{-3}$ deg and $\tilde{\Delta t} \approx 1$ μm) depicts a considerable variation. The difference between predefined and

Table 2
Validation of reference data generation on 3 complex shapes and testing of 4 objective functions.

Mechanical part	Median $\widetilde{\Delta\theta}$ ($\times 10^{-3}$ deg)		Absolute relative variation	Median $\widetilde{\Delta t}$ (μm)		Absolute relative variation	
	Unconstrained dataset pair	Reference dataset pair		Unconstrained dataset pair	Reference dataset pair		
impeller	OF_1	4.51	1.06	76 %	2.28	0.78	65 %
	OF_2	5.22	2.61	49 %	2.34	1.20	50 %
	OF_3	5.42	2.39	55 %	2.33	1.13	51 %
	OF_4	10.90	7.85	27 %	4.68	4.76	1 %
turbine blade	OF_1	3.35	1.12	66 %	2.61	0.84	67 %
	OF_2	3.61	1.97	45 %	3.09	1.49	51 %
	OF_3	4.25	2.07	51 %	3.29	1.70	48 %
	OF_4	10.73	9.88	15 %	9.72	7.98	17 %
winglet	OF_1	1.21	0.27	77 %	3.94	1.37	65 %
	OF_2	1.23	0.63	48 %	5.17	2.17	57 %
	OF_3	1.20	0.76	36 %	4.49	2.18	51 %
	OF_4	4.92	5.24	6 %	22.00	21.73	1 %

Fig. 12. Developed material standards for aeronautic applications.

estimated parameters in Table 2 depends on the inaccuracies in the formulation and minimization of the objective function ϕ_{ICP} (Eq. (1)) which is an approximation of the problem formulation ϕ (Eq. (14)).

For unconstrained dataset pairs, values of medians and confidence intervals are similar for OF_1 , OF_2 and OF_3 . For reference dataset pairs, the confidence intervals and medians for the ICP variant associated to OF_1 are smaller compared to the other three objective functions $OF_{i=2,3,4}$, which reveals the accuracy of ICP registration with point-to-quadratic objective function. In the case of impeller $\widetilde{\Delta\theta} = 1.06 \times 10^{-3}$ deg and $\widetilde{\Delta t} = 0.87 \mu\text{m}$, with absolute relative variations $> 65\%$ compared to the unconstrained dataset. Therefore, the use of reference dataset pairs is more suitable than unconstrained dataset pairs to evaluate registration algorithms and validate the most accurate ICP variant.

6. Application of the validated ICP variant on experimental datasets recorded with a machine vision system

6.1. Developed physical material standards (PMS)

The implemented ICP variant already validated on reference datasets, is tested on measured datasets recorded on a specific material standard developed for aeronautic applications (e.g., propellers, aircraft wing edges and ailerons). The PMS is a physical part with large dimensions and complex shape (Fig. 12(a)). It is made of aluminium material with dimensions $1000 \times 400 \times 60 \text{ mm}^3$. The main frame of the material standard contains ribs and holes. Additional eight secondary artefacts are developed with prismatic (stepped rectangular and circular pyramids) and freeform (parabolic cylinder, cylindrical paraboloid and elliptical paraboloid) surfaces (Fig. 12(b)). The secondary artefacts can be deposited in the main material standard frame on three spheres to

Fig. 13. Photo of the traceable accurate CMM (Zeiss UPMC carat) used for measuring the PMS including the main frame and secondary artefacts.

guarantee isostatic link and avoid clumping deformation. The PMS is measured with a traceable accurate Coordinate Measuring Machine (CMM) and a Structured Light (SL) system.

6.2. Calibration of the PMS with a traceable high-accurate CMM

A traceable accurate CMM equipped with a tactile probe is used for measuring the whole material standard including the main frame and secondary artefacts (Fig. 13). The used CMM is a Zeiss UPMC carat with a maximum measurement range of $1200 \times 850 \times 600 \text{ mm}^3$. The established measurement uncertainty is $0.7 + L/1200 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, where L is the length of the PMS. Measurements are carried out inside a cleanroom where the temperature is controlled to $20 \pm 0.3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The adopted paths are defined on the Zeiss software, with a step of $100 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ along the x -, y - and z -axis. The measured data on the sphere (a), cylinder (b), stepped rectangular pyramid (c) and stepped circular pyramid (d) are illustrated

Fig. 14. Measurements carried out with the traceable CMM.

in Fig. 14.

Validated TLS algorithms are applied to the measured data and the returned residuals between the analytical models (sphere and cylinder) or CAD (Computer-Aided Design) models (stepped pyramids) and the measured datapoints are shown in Fig. 15. The residuals are exploited such as to calculate Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Peak to Valley (PV) parameters, reported in Table 3. Since the measurement uncertainty of the traceable Zeiss CMM is below $3 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, the values of PV illustrated in Table 3 reveals the performance of the manufacturing machine tools. For the case of sphere, the form error could be estimated to about $26 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ that agree with common tolerances of milling machine tools.

6.3. Scanning of the PMS with a traceable SL system

The aluminium PMS is scanned again with the developed SL system traceable to the SI metre definition (Fig. 16). The traceable SL system includes: (1) two monochrome industrial cameras (Ximea MQ013rg-e2 equipped with digital lens LM8JCM-V of 8.5 mm focal length) and (2) an industrial projector (DLP Lightcrafter 4500) positioned below the cameras. The traceable SL system is set on the end-effector of a 6-axis Kawasaki RS003N industrial robot with a maximum 3D working range of $967 \times 620 \times 620 \text{ mm}^3$. The industrial robot is mounted on one additional unidirectional motion 7-axis of 1500 mm range to enlarge the working range and to scan large volume parts up to $2000 \times 1000 \times 1000 \text{ mm}^3$. The SL system is calibrated using Zhang's method [32] to estimate the intrinsic and extrinsic parameters for the camera and the projector.

The calibrated SL system is used for scanning the sphere, cylinder and stepped pyramids. Pre-processing including trimming, filtering and normal vectors estimation is applied. The filtering process allows to remove outliers. Normal vectors are calculated from the neighbouring points through covariance analysis and oriented consistently towards the camera. For each artefact, 2 scans are recorded and matched into the same coordinate system. Here, the first step consists in applying a coarse matching based on the coordinates of the 6-axis industrial robot and the seventh unidirectional motion axis. Afterwards, the validated ICP variant OF_1 is used for relative transformation refinement. Similar to

Fig. 15. Residuals: deviations between the nominal surface and measured data with the CMM.

Table 3

RMSE, MAE and PV calculated on CMM measurements.

Mechanical part	RMSE (μm)	MAE (μm)	PV (μm)
Semi sphere	3.33	2.69	29.39
Semi cylinder	6.40	4.33	35.56
Stepped rectangular pyramid	11.29	8.89	42.24
Stepped circular pyramid	3.56	2.85	19.34

CMM measurements, residuals are calculated for each scanned part and illustrated in Fig. 17. The distribution of residuals seems to be Gaussian and RMSE, MAE and PV are summarized in Table 4.

The comparison of the CMM measurements (Table 3) and SL scanning (Table 4) reveals that the SL scanning system is less accurate than CMM (for sphere, the difference could be estimated to about $350 \mu\text{m}$), although it returns a high number of datapoints. According to Weckenmann et al. [1], it is recommended that “no additional measurement uncertainty, which is significant compared to the uncertainty of the sensor data, should be generated”. This can be verified by the negligible errors for OF_1 in Table 2 compared to the residuals in Table 4.

7. Conclusion

Reference datasets are crucial for testing and validating algorithms dedicated to registration. In this context, a null-space data generation

approach was developed and implemented, adhering to the ISO 5436-2:2012 standard. The proposed approach is based on calculating deviations between points and their underlying surfaces, leading to the generation of misaligned dataset pairs with a known optimal rigid transformation. The generator’s effectiveness was validated by the negligible difference (approximately $10^{-12} \mu\text{m}$) observed between optimal and predefined transformation parameters. Furthermore, four variants of the ICP algorithm were evaluated using the generated reference dataset pairs. Monte-Carlo simulations were also conducted for uncertainty evaluation. Among the objective functions tested, the point-to-quadratic function was found to be the most accurate method for registration. Overall, by providing an unbiased performance measure, the evaluation of registration algorithms with reference datasets is more suitable than unconstrained datasets used in the literature.

The validated ICP variant with the point-to-quadratic objective function was then applied to data processed by a traceable Structured Light (SL) system. Comparisons of the residuals with those obtained from Coordinate Measuring Machine (CMM) measurements indicated a deviation of about $350 \mu\text{m}$, which could be deemed acceptable for inline inspection purposes.

The formulation of the registration problem could also be generalized to groupwise and cross-source registration algorithms intended to merge more than two measurements from sensors with various accuracies. These registration algorithms could then be evaluated with a reference data generator based on the generalized problem formulation.

Fig. 16. Traceable SL system: (a) CAD of the SL system and (b) photo of the experiment based on the traceable SL system.

Fig. 17. Residuals: deviations between the nominal surface and measured data with the SL system.

Table 4

RMSE, MAE and PV calculated on SL measurements.

Mechanical part	RMSE (μm)	MAE (μm)	PV (μm)
Semi sphere	25.01	20.21	121.01
Semi cylinder	26.85	21.72	128.34
Stepped rectangular pyramid	38.07	28.92	277.34
Stepped circular pyramid	34.63	29.17	238.44

Moreover, a complete evaluation procedure taking into consideration most factors that could influence the behaviour of registration algorithms should be established. This could be achieved with graded datasets (i.e., by computing a performance measure for each datum generated with an increasing degree of difficulty).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Louis-Ferdinand Lafon: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Alain Vissière**: Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Charyar Mehdi-Souzani**: Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Nabil Anwer**: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Hichem Nourira**: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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